

**PILOTS for robotic Inspection and maintenance
Grounded on advanced intelligent platforms and
prototype applications**

**Deliverable D4.3
PILOTING final robotic vehicles**

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Content

1. Introduction.....	13
1.1 Purpose of the Document	13
1.2 Scope of the Document	13
1.3 Structure of the Document	14
2. Aerial Robots.....	15
2.1 AEROX.....	15
2.1.1 General Overview	15
2.1.2 Modifications	15
2.1.2.1 Contact Device.....	15
2.1.2.2 End Effector.....	16
2.1.3 Final Version.....	17
2.1.4 Final Technical Specifications	20
2.2 AERO-CAM.....	22
2.2.1 General Overview	22
2.2.2 Modifications	22
2.2.3 Final Version.....	22
2.2.4 Final Technical Specifications	23
2.3 VIAD-DRONE.....	25
2.3.1 General Overview	25
2.3.2 Modifications	25
2.3.2.1 VIAD-DRONE Aerial Frame: Base Platform	25
2.3.2.2 Landing Gear Retractable Mechanism	26
2.3.2.3 Motorization and Propellers	27
2.3.2.4 Navigation Sensors	28
2.3.2.5 Caterpillar System	29
2.3.2.6 Cargo System: DDS (Dampened Drop System).....	31
2.3.2.7 Manipulator for Target Installation	33
2.3.3 Final Version.....	34
2.3.4 Final Technical Specifications	36

2.4	TTDRONE	37
2.4.1	General Overview	37
2.4.2	Modifications	38
2.4.2.1	TTDRONE Base Frame.....	38
2.4.2.2	Motorization and Propellers	40
2.4.2.3	Tethered System	40
2.4.2.4	Sensors Onboard.....	41
2.4.2.5	Electromagnets	41
2.4.3	Final Version.....	42
2.4.4	Final Technical Specifications	43
3.	Ground Robots.....	45
3.1	RISING.....	45
3.1.1	General Overview	45
3.1.2	Modifications	45
3.1.3	Final Version.....	45
3.1.4	Final Technical Specifications	48
3.2	CART	48
3.2.1	General Overview	49
3.2.2	Modifications	49
3.2.3	Final Version.....	50
3.2.4	Final Technical Specifications	52
3.3	UGV Robot.....	52
3.3.1	General Overview	52
3.3.2	Modifications	52
3.3.3	Final Version.....	53
3.3.4	Final Technical Specifications	54
4.	Crawlers and Hybrid Robots	56
4.1	BIKE.....	56
4.1.1	General Overview	56
4.1.2	Modifications	57

4.1.2.1	Gas Detection System.....	57
4.1.2.2	Cleaning System	58
4.1.2.3	Rolling Ultrasound Sensor.....	60
4.1.2.4	Inspection Camera	61
4.1.2.5	3D LIDAR	61
4.1.2.6	Deployment Tool.....	62
4.1.3	Final Version.....	64
4.1.4	Final Technical Specifications	65
4.2	HYBRID.....	68
4.2.1	General Overview	68
4.2.2	Modifications	68
4.2.2.1	Tilted Drone.....	68
4.2.2.2	Landing gear	70
4.2.2.3	Satellite Deployment System.....	72
4.2.2.4	Sensors for Relative Navigation	75
4.2.3	Final Version.....	82
4.2.4	Final Technical Specifications	82
5.	Conclusions.....	85

List of Figures

Figure 1. Aerox version 3 aerial robot.	15
Figure 2. Crawler parts prior to upgrade.	16
Figure 3. A close look at the changes made upon the mentioned parts of the probe mechanism.	17
Figure 4. General view of the AEROX platform.	17
Figure 5. Retracted arm example.	18
Figure 6. Latest version of the RMCP.	18
Figure 7. Close view of the roller probe mounted in the crawler.	19
Figure 8. Both external and internal close-up of the contact device rear end.	20
Figure 9. AERO-CAM RPA.	22
Figure 10. AERO-CAM aerial robot.	23
Figure 11. VIAD-DRONE modular concept.	25
Figure 12. Carbon fiber plates for attaching the various sensors to the chassis.	26
Figure 13. Configuration of the previous landing gear (left), configuration of the current landing gear (right).	27
Figure 14. Close-up view of the retractile landing gear, CAD (left) and picture of the built system (right).	27
Figure 15. MN4012-9-480kv (left), MN5006-450kv (right).	28
Figure 16. The sensors selected for the final version and their location on the platform.	29
Figure 17. Caterpillar system version in D4.1, CAD and built prototype.	30
Figure 18. Caterpillar system final version, CAD and built prototype.	31
Figure 19. Carbon fiber side plates of the caterpillar system in the D4.1 version and their removal in the final version.	31
Figure 20. Close-up view of DDS (Dampened Drop System).	32
Figure 21. Rotary damper FRT-C2-201.	32
Figure 22. Cargo system in version D4.1 (left), cargo system with DDS in the final version (right).	33
Figure 23. Cargo system-built prototype.	33
Figure 24. CAD of the manipulator for target installation mounted on the VIAD-DRONE version D4.1 (left) and the final version (right).	34
Figure 25. Close-up view of the CAD of the manipulator for target installation.	34

Figure 26. Final version of VIAD-DRONE in the bearing inspection configuration.....	35
Figure 27. Final version of VIAD-DRONE in the sensor box installation configuration.	35
Figure 28. Final version of VIAD-DRONE in the target installation configuration.	35
Figure 29. Final version CAD and main measurements of VIAD-DRONE.....	36
Figure 30: TTDRONE final version.	37
Figure 31. Tunnel inspection robotic system integrates a UGV and a UAV.....	38
Figure 32. Position of the shelf plate to place the various components under the UAV frame.....	39
Figure 33. Final version of the distribution of components on the platform.	39
Figure 34. TTDRONE quad-rotor configuration (left) and octa-rotor configuration (right).....	40
Figure 35. Real scenario where the UAV is connected to the UGV through the tethered system. ...	41
Figure 36. TTDRONE sensors distribution.	41
Figure 37. VEM25 24Vdc electromagnet.	42
Figure 38. Positioning of the UAV relative to the UGV for landing and take-off operations.....	42
Figure 39. Final version CAD and main measurements of TTDRONE.	43
Figure 40. (left) Thermographic image obtained by RISING. (right) RISING platform during the refinery experiments.	45
Figure 41. Both flippers of the Rising robot.	46
Figure 42. Previous and current flippers.....	46
Figure 43. Different rubber material of RISING tracks.....	46
Figure 44. Hot-swapping battery system.	47
Figure 45. Inductive plate in the bottom part of the RISING robot and Robot charging station with wireless charger.....	47
Figure 46. FLIR AX8 thermal camera + PTU.	48
Figure 47. CART vehicle.....	49
Figure 48. Camera payload, depth sensor and lighting options.	49
Figure 49. TTDrone with tethered cable from the CART.....	50
Figure 50. FARO laser scanner mounted on the CART.	51
Figure 51. SINTEF Nav Payload.	51
Figure 52. UGV platform overview.....	54
Figure 53. UGV digital twin.	54
Figure 54. End-effector with RGB-D camera and gripper.....	54

Figure 55. Custom gripper design.....	54
Figure 56. BIKE basic platform with spot measurement ultrasound sensor.....	56
Figure 57. BIKE application scenario.....	56
Figure 58. BIKE as upgraded in first period of PILOTING - already incorporating Gas Detection, Rolling UT sensor and with a cleaning brush option.....	57
Figure 59. Small ATEX sensor junction box design.	58
Figure 60. Mounting of smaller gas sensor junction box freeing up space for the 3D LIDAR on the BIKE.	58
Figure 61. Spacer discs mounted alongside brush.	59
Figure 62. Set of spacer discs for use with different types of brushes.....	59
Figure 63. Shifted protective cover and black marking on rotating shaft.....	60
Figure 64. Visibility from navigation camera (top) and inspection camera in forward position (bottom).....	60
Figure 65. Rolling ultrasound sensor mounting between the BIKE front-wheels.....	61
Figure 66. Mounting of inspection camera on BIKE.....	61
Figure 67. Rotating 2D laser range finder design and finished hardware.....	62
Figure 68. Mounting positions for the 3D scanning LIDAR.	62
Figure 69. Deployment tool for installation inside a flange or manway.....	63
Figure 70. Deployment tool for BIKE installed inside an actual flange.....	64
Figure 71. BIKE with 3D LIDAR, inspection camera and gas sensor.	64
Figure 72. BIKE with PILOTING extensions.	65
Figure 73. Top view Hybrid.....	70
Figure 74. Hybrid's landed on pipe view and perspective view.....	70
Figure 75. Approach phase.	71
Figure 76. Grasping phase.	71
Figure 77. Inspection phase.	72
Figure 78. Housing phase.....	72
Figure 79. Crawler descent in deployment phase.	73
Figure 80. Crawler adherence in deployment phase.....	74
Figure 81. Inspection Phase.	74
Figure 82. Crawler retrieval phase detail.....	75

Figure 83. Dovetail connector detail.....	75
Figure 84. Overall view - Relative navigation sensors.....	76
Figure 85. OSx Ouster LiDAR.....	76
Figure 86. Depth sensor Realsense D435i.....	77
Figure 87. Hokuyo UST 10LX LiDAR.....	77
Figure 88. Function avoidance between components.....	78
Figure 89. Hybrid system block diagram.....	78
Figure 90. On board sensors.....	79
Figure 91. On board crawler system.....	79
Figure 92. Custom autopilot.....	80
Figure 93. Power management.....	81
Figure 94. Motors / PC / connections.....	81
Figure 95. HYBRID system.....	82

List of Tables

Table 1. Robotic vehicles, types, and associated use-cases.	13
Table 2. Final AEROX specifications.....	20
Table 3. Final AERO-CAM specifications.	23
Table 4. Comparative between the motors MN4012-9-480kv and MN5006-450kv.....	28
Table 5. Final VIAD-DRONE specifications.	36
Table 6. Final TTDRONE specifications.....	43
Table 7. Final RISING specifications.	48
Table 8. Final CART specifications.....	52
Table 9. Final UGV Robot specifications.....	54
Table 10. Final BIKE specifications.	65
Table 11. Autopilot Specifications.....	69
Table 12. Final HYBRID specifications.	82

Acronyms

Abbreviation	Explanation
AC	Alternating current
AI	Artificial Intelligence
ATEX	Atmosphere Explosible
CAD	Computer Aided Design (software)
CANopen	CANopen is a communication protocol
DC	Direct Current
DDS	Dampened Drop System
DoF	Degrees of Freedom
GCS	Ground Control Station
GNSS	Global Navigation Satellite System
GSD	Ground Sampling Distance
HD	High Definition
HW	Hardware
IMU	Inertial Measurement Unit (sensor)
LIDAR	Light detection and ranging (sensor)
mAh	Electric Charge Unit (milli Ampere-Hours)
Modbus	Modbus is a data communications protocol
Mpx	Megapixel, also MP, number of pixel in a picture, indication of resolution.
MTOM	Maximum Take-Off Mass
MTOW	Maximum Take-Off Weight
Ncm	Torque Unit (Newton Centimeter)
NMC	Lithium-Nickel-Manganese-Cobalt-Oxide
RC	Remote Controlled (Vehicles)
RCS	Rich Communication Services
RGB	Red, Green and Blue
RPAS	Remotely Piloted Aircraft System
SLAM	Simultaneous Localization And Mapping
SW	Software
UAV	Unmanned Aerial Vehicle
USB	Universal Serial Bus
UGV	Unmanned Ground Vehicle
USE	University of Sevilla (Partner)
UT	Ultrasonic Testing
UTM	Ultrasonic Thickness Measurement

1. Introduction

1.1 Purpose of the Document

This document describes the final iteration of the robotics vehicles. It describes in detail all modifications and upgrades made to the vehicles described in D4.1. While some modifications had already been foreseen, others resulted from experiences during testing and field trials. Therefore, a special focus is placed on explaining the reasons that have led to changes and how those changes contribute to improving the respective robotic systems.

1.2 Scope of the Document

The D4.3 “PILOTING final robotic vehicles” deliverable covers the activities carried out within the WP4 “Adaptation of robotic vehicles and data gathering” to further develop and improve the PILOTING robotic vehicles (aerial robots, ground robots and crawlers and hybrid robots) during the second period of the project. Table 1 lists the robotic vehicles.

Table 1. Robotic vehicles, types, and associated use-cases.

Robotic vehicle	Type	Use-case scenario
AEROX	Aerial vehicle	Refinery large structures inspection
AERO-CAM	Aerial vehicle	Viaduct general visual inspection
VIAD-DRONE	Aerial vehicle	Viaduct bearing inspection
		Viaduct sensor installation
		Viaduct surveying target installation
TT-DRONE	Aerial vehicle	Tunnel local inspection
RISING	Ground vehicle	Refinery ground monitoring
CART	Ground vehicle	Tunnel general inspection
UGV	Ground vehicle	Refinery valve operation
BIKE	Crawler	Refinery vessel inspection
HYBRID	Hybrid	Refinery pipes inspection

1.3 Structure of the Document

This deliverable has been structured by type of robot, divided in aerial vehicles, ground vehicles, crawlers, and hybrid systems. Therefore, the document presents the following sections:

- **Section 1** specifies the purpose, scope, and structure of the document.
- **Section 2** describes improvements and further development done in relation to the aerial robots, containing AEROX, AERO-CAM, VIAD-DRONE and TTDRONE drones.
- **Section 3** describes improvements and further development done in relation to the ground robots, containing RISING and CART and UGV robots.
- **Section 4** describes improvements and further development done in relation to crawlers and hybrid robots, containing BIKE and HYBRID robots.
- **Section 5** contains the conclusions.

2. Aerial Robots

2.1 AEROX

2.1.1 General Overview

The AeroX is a specialized aircraft that performs physical contact inspection on surfaces using a robotic mobile contact platform (RMCP) equipped with wheels and inspection sensors. The AeroX is composed of a six degree-of-freedom (DoF) robotic arm and a semi-autonomous operation that allows for uninterrupted contact during autonomous flight. The robot uses internal sensors to maintain its position relative to the surface contact point, and its design allows for efficient compensation of perturbations such as wind. The AeroX can perform contact inspection on surfaces at any orientation and can easily be integrated into maintenance operations in various industries.

During this second period, it has been constructed the version 3 of this AeroX platform (see Figure 1), fulfilling all the specifications defined in deliverable D4.1.

Figure 1. Aerox version 3 aerial robot.

Below it will be commented the upgrades performed during this second period over the version v3 of this Aerox robot already specified in deliverable D4.1.

2.1.2 Modifications

2.1.2.1 Contact Device

As a way of quality-of-life improvement motivated by pilot feedback, the manipulator arm now quickly relays color-coded system information to the user on the ground. The latter is achieved by means of a LED placed in the rear end of the contact device, which is designed to be noticeable from our operational ranges. For instance, said light plays a fundamental role in telling the pilot when the contact pressure is high enough to enter in the autonomous contact mode.

2.1.2.2 End Effector

Based on the valuable experience gained during the field tests at Chevron's refinery, the end-effector of the system has undergone several significant upgrades. These upgrades have been specifically designed to address key areas of improvement, ensuring enhanced performance and reliability throughout the operation.

Previously, the rack tolerances (see Figure 2) were too loose for the sensor to achieve the desired accuracy, as even small deviations in perpendicularity could jeopardize the repeatability of the final measure. Furthermore, the traditionally employed gel had a noticeable high density, which meant that the couplant would be rapidly worn out as the roller probe moved along the inspection surface. Therefore, a noteworthy fraction of the available flight time was demanded by gel replenishment operations.

Figure 2. Crawler parts prior to upgrade.

The mentioned issues were tackled by means of tighter tolerances in the parts involved, as well as the addition of a guiding dovetail to the probe deployment mechanism. The latter included a small aperture that would house a new and less dense oily couplant (refer to Figure 3). As a result, these upgrades provided the end-effector with more accurate and consistent contact of the probe with the target surface.

Figure 3. A close look at the changes made upon the mentioned parts of the probe mechanism.

2.1.3 Final Version

The system's current appearance adheres to the initial specifications outlined in D4.1, while incorporating all previously mentioned modifications. The accompanying photographic evidence highlights several notable features, including the retractable propeller arms and landing gear, as well as the manipulator arm outfitted with its protective cover and the latest crawler iteration.

Figure 4. General view of the AEROX platform.

Figure 5. Retracted arm example.

Figure 6. Latest version of the RMCP.

Figure 7. Close view of the roller probe mounted in the crawler.

Figure 8. Both external and internal close-up of the contact device rear end.

2.1.4 Final Technical Specifications

Table 2. Final AEROX specifications.

SPEC_ID	Name and Description
RLS-Spec-01	Size of the robot (in mm)

RLS-Spec-02	Operating temperature: 0...+40 °C	
RLS-Spec-03	Maximum takeoff weight: 25 Kg	
RLS-Spec-04	Empty weight without batteries and contact device: 9 Kg	
RLS-Spec-05	Weight with standard equipment and batteries: 18 Kg	
RLS-Spec-06	Free-flight positioning precision using GNSS: Vertical 0,5 m, horizontal 1,5 m.	
RLS-Spec-07	Maximum wind resistance during contact: gusts of over 10 m/s	
RLS-Spec-08	Standard configuration flight time: 10 min	
RLS-Spec-09	Minimum surface curvature: 0,5 m radius	
RLS-Spec-10	Batteries specifications: 2 units of 6S (25 V) and 22 Ah capacity.	
RLS-Spec-11	Wireless communications over proprietary ubiquity Wi-Fi protocol.	
RLS-Spec-12	Cable communications over ethernet gigabit cable.	
RLS-Spec-13	UT sensor dual crystal probe	
RLS-Spec-14	UT sensor frequency 4 MHz	
RLS-Spec-15	UT sensor element diameter 8 mm	
RLS-Spec-16	UT sensor surface temperature 0°C ... 40°C	
RLS-Spec-17	UT sensor wall thickness range 3 ... 100 mm	
RLS-Spec-18	UT instrument Mistras 110-LAN	
RLS-Spec-19	UT software EuroscanV	

2.2 AERO-CAM

2.2.1 General Overview

In general terms, the AERO-CAM UAS is a hexacopter platform dedicated to vision inspection activities, this is derived from a DJI Matrice 600 Pro, which is a commercial UAV. This aerial robot's mission is to perform activities related to visual inspection of the underside of the viaduct deck and have cleaner pictures of the horizontal surfaces of the pilar and the rest of possible walls throughout its upper camera.

It is important to mention that under the viaduct, losses of GNSS signal are expected. For this reason, AERO-CAM integrates a LIDAR system between the two legs of the landing skid to estimate its global localization.

Figure 9. AERO-CAM RPA.

2.2.2 Modifications

The hardware architecture has not undergone any modification compared to the last version presented of the system in the deliverable D4.1 PILOTING first robotic vehicles. The AERO-CAM is the aerial robot, in which CATEC obtained the greatest advances at the hardware level. However, the UAS was improved in the area of software. These are presented in deliverable D5.3. Final version of advanced autonomous functionalities for aerial robots, focused on localization and control algorithms.

2.2.3 Final Version

As mentioned before, the design and development of the hardware were completed and presented in deliverable D4.1. PILOTING first robotic vehicles, showing the figures for each subsystem. Then, only a summary of the general components that configure the complete system are included to facilitate the comprehension of the deliverable as an independent document:

- **Airframe:**

The airframe used for the AERO-CAM is based on Matrice 600 pro with an A3 Pro autopilot, a Lightbridge 2 HD communication system and a set of Smart Batteries.

- **Camera:**

Sony alpha 7R IV, this camera has excellent characteristics for inspection missions.

- **Gimbal and Damper System:**

The Gimbal Gremsy T3 was considered the most suitable because it has the most advanced camera stabilizers, covering all the required surfaces. The gimbal is installed on a customized damper, to minimize the vibrations that are transmitted to the system during the flight.

- **LIDAR:**

Due to the loss of GNSS signal, a LIDAR was integrated to estimate the UAV position.

- **Communication System:**

The aircraft communication was divided in two different levels:

- Onboard the aircraft, the camera PC connects and communicates with the aircrafts companion computer central via Wifi.
- With the Ubiquity module installed onboard and on the RCS to communicate the companion computer and the gRCS and mRCS.

Figure 10. AERO-CAM aerial robot.

2.2.4 Final Technical Specifications

Table 3. Final AERO-CAM specifications.

SPEC_ID	Name and Description
AC_Spec_01	Size (in mm)

AC_Spec_02	MTOM 15.5 kg
AC_Spec_03	Stationary flight accuracy in P-GPS mode: Vertical: ± 0.5 m, Horizontal: ± 1.5 m
AC_Spec_04	Maximum climb speed: 5 m/s
AC_Spec_05	Maximum descend speed: 3 m/s
AC_Spec_06	Maximum wind resistance: 8 m/s
AC_Spec_07	Maximum speed: 60 km/h without wind
AC_Spec_08	Maximum endurance: 32 min without payload, 16 min with maximum payload.
AC_Spec_09	Battery type LiPo 6s
AC_Spec_10	Operational temperature (for the batteries): from -10°C to 40°C
AC_Spec_11	61 Mpx camera
AC_Spec_12	Camera ISO from 100 to 32000
AC_Spec_13	Two available lenses: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • General inspection: SONY ZEISS SONNAR 24/1.8 • Detailed inspection: SONY FE 85/1.8 (up to 0.1mm GSD)
AC_Spec_14	Full coverage of vertical surfaces
AC_Spec_15	Full coverage of horizontal and sloping surfaces
AC_Spec_16	Bottom surfaces partially covered
AC_Spec_17	No restrictions to fly far away distance from obstacle while GNSS is available
AC_Spec_18	In GNSS denied mode, range of flying far away from obstacles: 50m (LIDAR range)

AC_Spec_19	Minimum allowed distance to obstacle: ~3m front, ~2.5m overhead
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2.3 VIAD-DRONE

2.3.1 General Overview

The VIAD-DRONE is an aerial robot dedicated to the inspection of viaducts. Specifically, this vehicle is designed to perform three different tasks: bearing inspection, sensor box installation, and target installation. More details about these use cases can be found in deliverable D4.1. In all cases, the robot-viaduct interaction occurs, even moving into narrow spaces between the top of the pillar and the deck. To this end, the platform needs to be as small as possible while still being able to carry the payloads and tools required to complete the different missions. Consequently, a hybrid design of the VIAD-DRONE is proposed, where the base platform is adaptable to install different accessories depending on the use case. Figure 11 shows the final CAD design of the aerial robot to illustrate the modular concept and equipment mounted for each application. It is worth noting that the airframe with electronics and batteries, onboard computer, communication system, and navigation sensors form the standard base platform for each use case.

Figure 11. VIAD-DRONE modular concept.

2.3.2 Modifications

2.3.2.1 VIAD-DRONE Aerial Frame: Base Platform

Improve the robustness of the chassis by replacing 3D printed parts with carbon fiber ones. Specifically, this involves replacing the chassis supports where the various sensors used on the

platform (2D LIDAR, RealSense camera, altimeter) are mounted. Figure 12 illustrates the location of this part.

Figure 12. Carbon fiber plates for attaching the various sensors to the chassis.

2.3.2.2 Landing Gear Retractable Mechanism

Change and increase the length of the retractable landing gear (see Figure 13). The previous version consisted of two 16mm-diameter vertical carbon fiber tubes attached to a single 16mm horizontal tube responsible for supporting the platform on the ground. Currently, the platform is equipped with the Tarot X Series landing gear, it includes a single 25mm-diameter vertical carbon fiber tube attached to a 16mm-diameter horizontal tube with a length of 440mm. In addition, as shown in Figure 14, it has a retractable mechanism made of machined 6061T6 aluminum.

Furthermore, the total height of the platform with the landing gear not retracted is increased from 280 mm to 530 mm. This change allows the gimbal and inspection camera to be mounted on the lower part of the platform. However, the sensor box installation application requires retracting the landing gear, reducing the total height to 288.5 mm. The platform must have access to the work area, where the sensor box is placed to measure the vibrations of the viaduct. As mentioned in D4.1, this area is typically between 30 and 60 cm for most viaducts.

Figure 13. Configuration of the previous landing gear (left), configuration of the current landing gear (right).

Figure 14. Close-up view of the retractile landing gear, CAD (left) and picture of the built system (right).

2.3.2.3 Motorization and Propellers

The motorization and diameter of the propellers of the VIAD-DRONE vehicle are modified because of the high weight of the platform. As reported by the pilots, although the aerial robot flew well in terms of power, it was at the limit of its capabilities.

The changes aim to improve the thrust and efficiency of the platform. The conclusions presented have been obtained through a theoretical comparative study between the MN4012-9-480kv motor (used by the previous platform) and the MN5006-450kv motor (which offers high performance at a low weight). Figure 15 show the two motors involved in the study.

Figure 15. MN4012-9-480kv (left), MN5006-450kv (right).

Table 4. Comparative between the motors MN4012-9-480kv and MN5006-450kv.

MODEL	WEIGHT PER MOTOR	TOTAL WEIGHT	PROPELLER SIZE	THRUST AT 50% THROTTLE	EFFICIENCY AT 50% (THRUST/POWER)	THRUST AT 65% THROTTLE	EFFICIENCY AT 65% (THRUST/POWER)
MN4012-9-480kv	128g	1024g	14"	1170g	7.53	1530g	6.89
MN5006-450kv	106g	848g	15"	1084g	8.51	1643g	7.2

Table 4 gives the most relevant data for decision making. The comparison was made using a throttle of 50% and 65%, as these values are considered optimal throttle levels. On the one hand, at 50% throttle, the previous version (MN4012-9-480kv) provides more thrust but has lower efficiency and is heavier. On the other hand, at 65% throttle, the new motors (MN5006-450kv) outperform the old ones in all aspects. In this case, there would be 113g more thrust and 22g less weight per motor, resulting in 904g more thrust and 176g less weight overall. In addition, the new motors have higher thrust-to-power efficiency, giving the platform greater autonomy.

Concerning the size of the propeller, experimental tests were carried out to determine the optimal size. The autonomy was tested with 14" propellers and then with 15" propellers under the same flight conditions and throttle percentages. Initially, it was assumed that the 15" propellers would consume more power, resulting in a shorter flight time. However, the results showed otherwise. The larger propellers gave the platform more thrust at lower throttle, allowing the same thrust to be achieved with less throttle, reducing power consumption, and increasing flight time. Furthermore, the 15" propellers also provided advantages such as improved platform stability and greater thrust, resulting in better piloting maneuverability.

2.3.2.4 Navigation Sensors

As mentioned in D4.1, when flying below and close to a viaduct, the GNSS signal might not be reliable enough to perform safe navigation. Moreover, the accuracy in the localization is an essential requirement for the system. Therefore, the aerial robot needs to rely on some sensors for localization and safe navigation through the scenario.

To reduce the weight of the platform, efforts were made to optimize the number of sensors used in it. For this reason, experimental studies were conducted, which confirmed that the number of monocular cameras could be reduced to a single camera without compromising the results obtained (unlike the configuration used on the D4.1 platform, which used two cameras). Therefore, the sensors selected for the final version consist of a monocular camera (facing downward), an altimeter, and a 2D LIDAR with a mirror to simultaneously detect the pillar and the deck (see Figure 16).

Figure 16. The sensors selected for the final version and their location on the platform.

2.3.2.5 Caterpillar System

In the D4.1 version, the caterpillar system had two passive wheels and one active wheel (a motorized wheel with gears) placed in the center of the caterpillar (see Figure 17). After the initial experimental tests, it was found that the platform did not have enough traction to move correctly using the caterpillar system when it was attached to the roof of the viaduct. The reason was that the commercial caterpillar was not tight enough and only contacted the active wheel at the highest point. As a result, this wheel did not transmit all the torque provided by the motor to the caterpillar, and therefore the platform did not operate optimally.

Figure 17. Caterpillar system version in D4.1, CAD and built prototype.

As shown in Figure 18, the solution to this problem was to add a third passive wheel to tension the caterpillar. The new arrangement provided the necessary traction for the caterpillar system to move the platform forward on the roof of the viaduct.

Figure 18. Caterpillar system final version, CAD and built prototype.

However, the new design would increase the weight of the caterpillar system compared to the version presented in D4.1, whose weight was 423g. For this reason, it was decided to remove the carbon fiber side plates (see Figure 19). Initially, these parts were installed to increase rigidity, but it was later realized that they were not required. Removing these plates would mitigate the added weight in the new arrangement, resulting in a total weight of 451g in the final configuration.

Figure 19. Carbon fiber side plates of the caterpillar system in the D4.1 version and their removal in the final version.

2.3.2.6 Cargo System: DDS (Dampened Drop System)

The system responsible for dropping the sensor box has been enhanced with a new passive subsystem, the Dampened Drop System (DDS). The design allows for improved maneuverability without the need for additional electronics. Previously, there was a system whose function was to drop the box

once it reached the desired zone by activating some linear actuators. With the implementation of the new passive subsystem, the box can now be deposited onto the viaduct in a controlled manner, without risking damage to the box or the sensors inside it. It also ensures that the position of the sensor box is accurate after dropping.

Figure 20. Close-up view of DDS (Dampened Drop System).

The design of the new DDS (Dampened Drop System) subsystem is shown in Figure 20 and consists of two FRT-C2-201 rotary dampers (see Figure 21) as the main components. These dampers have a damping torque of 2 ± 0.6 Ncm and make it possible to attenuate the fall of the sensor box after the activation of the two linear actuators (previously used in the D4.1 version). With this improvement, a controlled and safe drop of the sensor box is achieved.

Figure 21. Rotary damper FRT-C2-201.

The FRT-C2-201 rotary dampers are connected to the coils through shafts. A nylon rope is wound around the coils. One end of the nylon rope is tied to the box holders. The other end is tied to a metal shaft that passes through the coils. The purpose is to release from the coils when all the rope is unwound, allowing the box to drop onto the viaduct and the platform to maneuver back to the base. Figure 22 shows the two complete systems. On the one hand, the housing supports, the DDS supports, and the coils are shown in blue. On the other hand, the shafts connecting the rotary dampers to the coils are colored red.

Figure 22. Cargo system in version D4.1 (left), cargo system with DDS in the final version (right).

To sum up, the sensor box has gone from being dropped onto the area where the viaduct bearings are located to being precisely and carefully deposited through the passive DDS System in charge of damping the maneuver. Figure 23 shows the position of this system on the aerial platform.

Figure 23. Cargo system-built prototype.

2.3.2.7 Manipulator for Target Installation

As shown in Figure 24, the location of the manipulator system was changed after experimental testing. It was moved from the top of the platform to the bottom. In addition, the inclination of the pole is corrected so that in the final configuration it is perpendicular to the surface where the sticker is to be applied. This improves the maneuverability of the touch-and-go task. Note that the reference axes of the platform were rotated -90° in yaw, as the orientation of the pole was changed (see Figure 24).

Figure 24. CAD of the manipulator for target installation mounted on the VIAD-DRONE version D4.1 (left) and the final version (right).

Two carbon fiber clamps bolted to a carbon fiber plate attached to the chassis have been used to fix the pole. Figure 25 shows the different components that make up the final system.

Figure 25. Close-up view of the CAD of the manipulator for target installation.

2.3.3 Final Version

After a detailed description of each of the modifications/improvements of the VIAD-DRONE vehicle design, some pictures of the final platform are presented. Figure 27 illustrate the final version of the aerial robot to perform bearing inspection, sensor box inspection, and target installation, respectively. Each picture shows the equipment installed on the platform to complete its specific task. Finally, the

general measurements of the VIAD-DRONE are given, as its technical specifications will be detailed in the following section.

Figure 26. Final version of VIAD-DRONE in the bearing inspection configuration.

Figure 27. Final version of VIAD-DRONE in the sensor box installation configuration.

Figure 28. Final version of VIAD-DRONE in the target installation configuration.

Figure 29. Final version CAD and main measurements of VIAD-DRONE.

2.3.4 Final Technical Specifications

Table 5. Final VIAD-DRONE specifications.

SPEC_ID	Name and Description
VD-Spec-01	Weight: 7750g
VD-Spec-02	Maximum take-off weight (MTOW): 8120g
VD-Spec-03	Flight time with MTOW: 10 min
VD-Spec-04	Size (LxWxH): 650 x 700 x 530 mm

VD-Spec-05	Power supply: 2x 6S 4500 mAh LiPo batteries
VD-Spec-06	Minimum clearance for sensor deployment: 90cm (width) x 30cm (height)
VD-Spec-07	Size of the sensor box (LxWxH): 115 x 90 x 55 mm

2.4 TTDRONE

2.4.1 General Overview

TTDRONE is an aerial platform developed to inspect tunnels (see Figure 30). This use case involves an Unmanned Ground Vehicle (UGV) and an Unmanned Aerial Vehicle (UAV), both of which are described in detail in D4.1. Figure 33 shows the integration of these two vehicles. As mentioned in D4.1, the TTDRONE platform aims to perform a comprehensive inspection of the tunnel to detect defects in the infrastructure. It does this by capturing images and analyzing them using artificial intelligence algorithms.

Figure 30: TTDRONE final version.

With respect to the UGV, this vehicle enables a general inspection of the tunnel. The tethered system allows the UAV to be connected to the UGV. That means that both power and data are transmitted from the UGV to the UAV using a cable connection. The fact that the TTDRONE is connected to the UGV by cable represents a great advantage, not just in terms of data transfer but also in terms of power supply. In this way, it does not rely solely on the autonomy provided by the LiPo battery, thus increasing the inspection time.

Figure 31. Tunnel inspection robotic system integrates a UGV and a UAV.

2.4.2 Modifications

D4.1 presented the first CAD design of the TTDRONE vehicle, although it was not manufactured until later. During the initial assembly and testing, some changes were identified as necessary to fulfil the specified tasks.

2.4.2.1 TTDRONE Base Frame

The TTDRONE vehicle is designed to carry both the perception system and the aerial module. The TTDRONE perception system consists of an Intel NUC i7 processing unit, the same as that used in the VIAD-DRONE, the Gremsy S1V3 gimbal, and the Sony A6400 camera, which are described in detail in D4.1, together with the aerial module.

The first decision was to keep the aerial module in the lower part of the platform. Thus, the micro-tether could be connected to the UAV without interfering with the other systems. As a result, the aerial module is mounted on the shelf plate of the platform. It should be noted that the shelf is a carbon fiber plate that is attached to the chassis at a sub-height using aluminum spacers (refer to Figure 32). In this way, the TTDRONE has a 90mm height space that allows it to transport the different components required for flight. The components and their distribution within the platform will be described in more detail later.

Figure 32. Position of the shelf plate to place the various components under the UAV frame.

After positioning the aerial module, the remaining components were distributed within the available space between the frame plate and the shelf plate (see Figure 32). The aim was to avoid extending the 90mm aluminum spacers, as there is a height limit due to proximity to the ground plane. To achieve this, the most optimized and compact component layout was sought, resulting in the configuration shown in Figure 33.

Figure 33. Final version of the distribution of components on the platform.

In the final distribution of the TTDRONE, the Intel NUC i7 is attached to the frame plate. For this, a new 3D printed box was designed to reduce the weight and size of the commercial box that originally accommodated the onboard computer. Underneath it, fixed to the shelf plate, is the Arduino box, whose Arduino is responsible for controlling the operation of the electromagnets (which will be described in detail in the following sections). Also, there is the POE (Power over Ethernet) used to power and connect the Ubiquity Bullet 5GHz (the same one used in the VIAD-DRONE) to the Intel NUC i7, a USB hub that acts as a power outlet for several of the platform's components, and finally the backup battery. The emergency battery, which the platform uses to perform landings in the event of a loss of connection through the tethered system, is specified in D4.1.

2.4.2.2 Motorization and Propellers

The TTDRONE, with all its components installed on the platform, is heavy, mainly due to the weight of the aerial module, the Gremsy S1V3 gimbal, and the Sony A6400 camera and lens. The total weight of the UAV is 7640g, and the quad-rotor configuration initially proposed does not provide the total thrust required. For this reason, a study has been carried out to find a new configuration that would allow us to fly the TTDRONE.

The dimensions of the platform are limited, as it must be a small and compact UAV that can perform take-off and landing maneuvers on the CART rooftop with a minimum of effort. This requirement immediately ruled out the hexa-rotor configuration as it would involve modifications to the platform frame. Therefore, instead an octa-rotor coaxial configuration was chosen (see Figure 34). The selected configuration provided the necessary thrust, improved maneuverability, and enhanced stabilization of UAV flight. This enabled the platform to fly with the tethered system, perception system, and onboard computer (Intel NUC i7).

Figure 34. TTDRONE quad-rotor configuration (left) and octa-rotor configuration (right).

2.4.2.3 Tethered System

The tethered system is the same as described in D4.1. The position of the system is inside the CART. Figure 35 shows the feasibility of flying the UAV in conjunction with the UGV.

Figure 35. Real scenario where the UAV is connected to the UGV through the tethered system.

2.4.2.4 Sensors Onboard

The designed platform has the same size constraints as the VIAD-DRONE, hence the payload limitations. Figure 36 shows the robot sensor distribution, which consists of two 2D LiDAR sensors for approaching the robot position using different sections of the tunnel, and a beacon for UAV localization relative to the UGV position (beacon emitting sensors). The configuration was chosen to achieve an optimal estimation of the UAV position in the workspace. The TTDRONE localization methods are described in detail in D5.3.

Figure 36. TTDRONE sensors distribution.

2.4.2.5 Electromagnets

The VEM25 24Vdc electromagnets are used in the TTDRONE vehicle for the take-off and landing maneuver, as well as for attaching the platform to the CART roof while in motion. There is one electromagnet per leg and their mounting on the platform is shown in Figure 37.

Figure 37. VEM25 24Vdc electromagnet.

Electromagnets are a fundamental component of the aerial robot, and their use has also made it possible to dispense with the metal plate carried on the UGV roof. Now, the TTDRONE is attached directly to the CART's metal roof (Figure 38), making UAV-UGV interaction much easier.

Figure 38. Positioning of the UAV relative to the UGV for landing and take-off operations.

2.4.3 Final Version

After the detailed description of each modification/improvement of the design of the TTDRONE vehicle, Figure 39 illustrates the CAD of the final version of the platform, as well as the general measurements of the TTDRONE. Finally, the technical specifications of the UAV will be detailed in the next section.

Figure 39. Final version CAD and main measurements of TTDRONE.

2.4.4 Final Technical Specifications

Table 6. Final TTDRONE specifications.

SPEC_ID	Name and Description
TT-Spec-01	Weight: 7645g
TT-Spec-02	MTOW: 7980g
TT-Spec-03	Diameter (including blades): 1022mm
TT-Spec-03	Size (LxWxH): 521x521x427mm
TT-Spec-05	Distance motor to motor: 640mm
TT-Spec-06	24V power supply from the aerial module of tethered system
TT-Spec-07	Safety battery: 6S LiPo 1000mAh and 100C

TT-Spec-08	Motor power consumption: 506W in hover
TT-Spec-09	Inspection image resolution: 6000x4000 (24MP)
TT-Spec-10	GSD: 0.098mm/pixel (40mm focal length and 1m of distance to the wall)
TT-Spec-11	Inspection image footprint: 588x392mm (40mm focal length and 1m of distance to the wall)
TT-Spec-12	Gimbal maximum angle speed: 180°/s
TT-Spec-13	Gimbal maximum angle range: $\pm 345^\circ$ in yaw, $\pm 120^\circ$ in pitch and $\pm 45^\circ$ in roll

3. Ground Robots

3.1 RISING

3.1.1 General Overview

RISING is a mobile manipulator specially designed for inspection and intervention. The concept aims for high mobility, robust, modular, easily transportable, and easy to deploy robot platform. In the context of PILOTING, redesigning the first version of the RISING mobile platform to comply with the application specifics has been the main issue targeted.

3.1.2 Modifications

Major adaptations have been performed into the RISING robot with the steering towards a different manipulator. For the times that RISING can go without the Kinova arm, the focus is put into better capabilities for the ground monitoring use case. The efforts towards improving the capabilities of the RISING robot have been dealing with are the following.

- Automatic inspection at ground level
- Easy battery extraction and wireless charging station
- Thermal and visual inspection
- Obstacle overcoming and avoidance.

A remarkable effort has to do with the second iteration of the robot traction system, looking after a more flexible set of grippers that provide a potential higher clearance when needed.

Figure 40. (left) Thermographic image obtained by RISING. (right) RISING platform during the refinery experiments.

3.1.3 Final Version

One of the most important components are the flippers, directly translating the motor movement against the floor. The flipper component consists of a belt track with interchangeable studs that allows the robot to move and navigate properly on many surfaces. There is one flipper per each side of the platform.

Figure 41. Both flippers of the Rising robot.

These flippers are controlled by a drive via a position loop, which receives the position reference from a relative incremental encoder. With this positioning method, it is necessary to integrate a reference signal that indexes one point along the entire flipper travel. This reference point is taken with an inductive sensor that activates a digital input of the controller when the detection happens.

The final version features a noticeable different construction of the flippers.

Figure 42. Previous and current flippers.

The last flipper design allows 4-5 different configurations based on which support surface with different height is contacting the floor. Some highlights on the different configurations are:

- Shorter surfaces configuration requires higher torque to rotate.
- Larger surfaces against steps make easier to climb.
- Different material for rubber tracks is needed depending on how erosive the floor material is.

Figure 43. Different rubber material of RISING tracks.

Another relevant update has to do with the change of batteries and specific focus on its easy extraction. This, together with the wireless charging feature makes the robot easier and safer to be operated.

The main advantage in this case is to make the battery swappable without any tools thanks to its special connector mounted in-house. Following figures show the battery model and a virtual 3D reconstruction that shows how the battery can be extracted from one side of the platform.

The battery model is a now an off-the-shelf VARTA Easy Blade 48V. This battery has 1502Wh of power and its technology is Lithium-Nickel-Manganese-Cobalt-Oxide (NMC). Its communications are through CANopen bus, and it has a BMS integrated which controls the cells voltages level and the thresholds of the charge and discharge current. The integration of such communication with the RISING system is also something to be highlighted.

The new battery provides more power instantly and with that the motors can reach the peak current power longer and more often. In addition, one of the most decisive aspects in this application is the total weight of the platform, with this new battery the total weight is reduced by 8kg, which leads to better performance and lower consumption of the system.

Figure 44. Hot-swapping battery system.

Figure 45. Inductive plate in the bottom part of the RISING robot and Robot charging station with wireless charger.

In this regard, we can also highlight both options for the robot to charge, either the external battery charger for swapping or the inductive charger unit. For the second option, a dedicated design of a charger station that can host such unit was also developed.

The final highlight has to do with the thermal imaging capabilities of the RISING robot, which was modified due to a discontinuation of the previously selected FLIR Duo Pro in favor of the FLIR AX8 camera together with a pan-tilt unit.

Figure 46. FLIR AX8 thermal camera + PTU.

The adoption of this camera also implied a change on the powering and communication options as the camera feed is facilitated through TCP/IP and a PoE connection is needed.

3.1.4 Final Technical Specifications

Table 7. Final RISING specifications.

SPEC_ID	Name and Description
RIS-Spec-01	860mm x 650mm x 250mm retracted flippers. Clearance configurations: 71mm, 115mm, 155mm
RIS-Spec-02	Operating temperature: 0...+40 °C
RIS-Spec-03	Weight: 100 kg
RIS-Spec-04	48V 30A LiFePo4 Battery
RIS-Spec-05	4g and Wi-Fi communication
RIS-Spec-06	IP65 protection class
RIS-Spec-07	Skid steering, 2 traction motors, 2 elevation motors
RIS-Spec-08	Max Speed: ± 2.5 m/s
RIS-Spec-09	Max Slope: 30°, Steps: 190mm

3.2 CART

3.2.1 General Overview

Figure 47. CART vehicle.

Robotnik's Cart vehicle is a UGV based on an off-the-shelf electric cart. Motion sensors provide an odometry estimate for the vehicle and together with different cameras, IMU's and Lidars, the robot can navigate autonomously or be teleoperated.

With RWD Ackermann kinematics its traction is controlled by an AC motor with an incremental encoder and modifications have been done to control the direction through a power steering system with an absolute encoder. The vehicle also allows an operator to take control anytime, even while sitting on it, but also implementing local and remote e-stop that actuate front and rear drum brakes.

3.2.2 Modifications

The cart vehicle has received small upgrades regarding the hardware and more specifically, the sensor payload. Different changes on the lifting mechanism have been tested, together with configurations of the camera balancing system. It is important to highlight that the 3 different configurations of lighting devices to cope with different conditions and looking for a better performance of the AI algorithms. The speed control and the camera shooting system has been also reworked in order to allow a continuous data capture while keeping the camera parameters (ISO, aperture, etc.).

Figure 48. Camera payload, depth sensor and lighting options.

The cabling from the AC power source (inverter) and up to the tethered drone system has been reworked together with a better allocation of the subsystem.

Figure 49. TTDrone with tethered cable from the CART.

System connectivity has also been enhanced thanks to a dedicated PTP multiband antennas, together with a complete rework configuration of the local networks.

3.2.3 Final Version

The CART vehicle is based on the autonomous vehicle of Robotnik's portfolio, which is already having the needed modification for teleoperation or basic autonomous driving together with the needed safety devices such as the remote e-stop. Additional devices mounted in the CART start with the communication subsystem based on AIRMAX Wi-Fi devices (Ubiquity)

The final version of the robotic vehicle is featuring an enhanced controller that can cope with different slopes with a better performance. Other improvements are related with the inspection payload and navigation payload.

The inspection payload final version is composed of:

- lifting column (which Modbus control is integrated with the robotic vehicle)
- the stabilization device ZION
- Gremsy T7 gimbal with a dedicated set of LED lighting solution.
- Sony alpha 7IVR camera + 24mm/80mm lenses.
- Depth ultrasonic sensor TERABEE

Apart from these fixed devices, a mounting support plus communication ROS node are in place for taking advantage of the FARO laser scanner solution.

To end with, the Phoenix Smart inverter together with the ad hoc cabling solution accommodates the use of the TTDrone for the local inspection.

Figure 50. FARO laser scanner mounted on the CART.

On the other hand, a dedicated navigation payload has been developed by SINTEF to cope with tunnel and GNSS denied environment and has been accommodated in the front part of the CART vehicle.

The navigation payload contains sensors that are used for mapping and localization of the CART. The sensors are an Ouster OS0 360-degree lidar, a camera, an IMU, a router and an onboard computer the executes the SLAM software.

The navigation payload has been updated with a new metal encapsulation that will make it more robust, based on the learnings from several hardware problems during the initial experiments (as described in D8.1). The metal profiles in the casing also help cooling the lidar. A DC/DC converter integrated in the payload reduces the risk of failures due to power quality issues and enables more flexibility in the use of different power sources. The payload is now connected to the main onboard computer through a dedicated Ethernet interface, rather than using the router on the CART. This is to have control of the load on the interface so that it can be used to synchronize sensor data between the navigation payload and the CART using PTP. These modifications shall address previous challenges with unreliable data and synchronization between the payload and the CART.

Figure 51. SINTEF Nav Payload.

3.2.4 Final Technical Specifications

Table 8. Final CART specifications.

SPEC_ID	Name and Description
CA-Spec-01	Dimensions: 2.727 x 1.444 x 2.082 mm
CA-Spec-02	Weight: 800 Kg
CA-Spec-03	Payload: 2 people + 227 kg in the rear box
CA-Spec-04	Speed: 35 Km/h
CA-Spec-05	Autonomy: Up to 70 km
CA-Spec-06	Temperature range: 0° to +40°C
CA-Spec-07	Maximum slope: 30%
CA-Spec-08	Batteries: Lead Acid 240Ah@48V
CA-Spec-09	Traction motors: 7,5 Kw AC
CA-Spec-10	Traction system: Ackermann, Rear Wheel / 4 XX

3.3 UGV Robot

3.3.1 General Overview

The UGV platform is a ground robot equipped with a manipulator and thus capable of complex manipulation tasks. The platform consists of a skid-steered mobile base and a 7-DoFs torque-controlled robot arm, which can provide force feedback during interaction with the environment. Please note that neither the mobile base nor the manipulator have been developed under PILOTING project. The mobile base has been selected because of its availability to ETHZ team and payload capability to carry the manipulator and its control box. The manipulator selection is explained in more detail in section 3.3.2. A custom 2-finger robotic gripper, which simplifies the grasping and turning of valves, is mounted on the end-effector. This contrasts with the initial proposal of using the Robotiq 2F gripper as the custom-made gripper adapts better to the use case of hand wheel valve manipulation. A digital twin of the entire platform exists and simplifies simulation as well as collision detection.

3.3.2 Modifications

Most of the work regarding the UGV has been dealing with the adaptation of the vehicle and its components to the specific needs for manipulation in the inspection and maintenance tasks, and even more considering the detailed constraints of the envisioned applications in refineries.

The UGV base is able to operate in typical conditions found in refineries, such as in concrete, gravel, or grated areas. To keep the platform modular, a groove plate on top of the robot base allows flexible

extension with other components. The sensors have been selected in a way to enable safe navigation in large areas and conduct reliable detection of desired objects.

The manipulator chosen is the Franka Emika Panda arm. The decision to change the initially chosen Kinova Gen3 arm to the Franka Emika Panda arm was driven by the results of hardware tests. During the initial tests with the Kinova Gen3 arm, it was found to have poor torque tracking and sensing capabilities, lacked fail-safe mechanisms, and was sensitive to breakage. These limitations raised concerns about the arm's reliability and performance in valve manipulation task. As an alternative, the Franka Emika Panda arm was subjected to follow-up tests, which demonstrated excellent tracking and a robustly tested platform. The Panda arm's torque tracking capabilities, coupled with its proven reliability, made it the preferred choice for integration and algorithm development for our use case.

3.3.3 *Final Version*

The key components of the UGV platform can be summarized as follows:

- Four-wheeled skid-steer mobile base including battery.
- 3D lidar for mapping and localization.
- Visual-inertial tracking camera.
- Franka Emika 7-DoF torque-controlled robotic arm.
 - Control box with battery-powered supply.
 - Wrist-mounted RealSense RGB-D camera for object detection.
 - Custom gripper design for grasping of circular hand-wheel valves.

Figure 52. UGV platform overview.

Figure 53. UGV digital twin.

Figure 54. End-effector with RGB-D camera and gripper.

Figure 55. Custom gripper design.

3.3.4 Final Technical Specifications

Table 9. Final UGV Robot specifications.

SPEC_ID	Name and Description
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UGV-Spec-01	Dimensions: 850mm x 850mm x 1500mm
UGV-Spec-02	Operating temperature: 0...+30 °C
UGV-Spec-03	Weight: 100 kg base + ~30 kg payload + 28 kg robot arm
UGV-Spec-04	3x 12 V DC lead-acid batteries (nominal system voltage 36 V DC)
UGV-Spec-05	4G and Wi-Fi communication
UGV-Spec-07	Mobility: Skid steering, 4 wheels, 4-wheel motors
UGV-Spec-08	Max Speed: ± 1.0 m/s
UGV-Spec-09	Max Slope: 10%
UGV-Spec-10	Manipulation: 7-DoFs compliant, torque-controlled robot arm including control box, custom gripper design for grasping of circular hand-wheel valves
UGV-Spec-11	Sensing: 3D lidar, visual-inertial tracking camera, wrist-mounted RGB-D camera for object detection
UGV-Spec-12	Safety: Wireless e-stop, compliance in robot arm control

4. Crawlers and Hybrid Robots

4.1 BIKE

4.1.1 General Overview

The purpose of the BIKE inspection robot is mainly internal inspection of ferromagnetic confined space structures such as pressure-vessels, pipes and storage tanks. The hand-deployable inspection crawler adheres to the surface by permanent magnets in the wheels and is controlled via a tether cable.

Figure 56. BIKE basic platform with spot measurement ultrasound sensor.

Figure 57. BIKE application scenario.

In a first iteration during period one of the PILOTING projects, the BIKE was equipped with a Gas-Detection system and a cleaning tool. Localization was performed with an existing static 2D LIDAR sensor solution.

Figure 58. BIKE as upgraded in first period of PILOTING - already incorporating Gas Detection, Rolling UT sensor and with a cleaning brush option.

4.1.2 Modifications

4.1.2.1 Gas Detection System

While the gas-detection system proved reliable and working, the sensor integration on the BIKE was consuming relevant mounting space and payload weight. Figure 58 shows how the gas sensor junction box occupies the entire volume on the left side of the BIKE.

The original design was based on an ATEX Zone 1 certified junction box, which allowed for safe monitoring concentration of combustible gas even once the robot had to be de-energized due to gas build-up.

To maintain this capability and to simultaneously reduce the size of the on-board unit, a custom explosion-proof sensor junction housing was designed. The new housing is conforming to the ATEX standard for pressure housings and will be certified to ATEX Zone 1 after the completion of the PILOTING project, mainly because the cost for certification is not covered by the project and due to the expected duration of the certification process.

Figure 59. Small ATEX sensor junction box design.

Figure 60. Mounting of smaller gas sensor junction box freeing up space for the 3D LIDAR on the BIKE.

4.1.2.2 Cleaning System

The purpose of the cleaning system is to prepare a corroded or dirty surface for ultrasonic thickness measurements. The first version (as shown by Figure 58) was tested during the PILOTING field trials and only minor modifications had to be implemented afterwards.

Findings from field trials were the following:

- Surface pressure of brush was not constant.
- Operator had no visual or other feedback if the brush is rotating.
- Forward visibility for navigation is very limited.

Spacer Discs for constant brush offset

The brush pressure offset was mitigated by a set of distance-maintaining discs (as shown by Figure 62), mountable on each side of the brush to achieve more. Figure 61 shows a set of discs mounted near the brush.

Figure 61. Spacer discs mounted alongside brush.

Figure 62. Set of spacer discs for use with different types of brushes.

The visual feedback of brush rotation was enabled by sliding the protection sheet to one side and marking the rotating shaft. Figure 63 shows the cover shifted (to the right in this view). The shifting of the protective cover also achieved better visibility at least on one side. Figure 64 shows visibility of the rotating shaft part from the navigation camera and the improved forward visibility from the navigation camera.

Figure 63. Shifted protective cover and black marking on rotating shaft.

Figure 64. Visibility from navigation camera (top) and inspection camera in forward position (bottom).

4.1.2.3 Rolling Ultrasound Sensor

A requirement for the thickness reading system is to be able to perform raster-scans covering an area of interest. This was not possible with the original sensor and probe-deployment system. The

development of the rolling probe was already completed prior to the field testing and no modifications were required afterwards.

Figure 65. Rolling ultrasound sensor mounting between the BIKE front-wheels.

4.1.2.4 Inspection Camera

An HD inspection camera with motorized tilt, strong controlled illumination and parallel laser dots for sizing was included on the BIKE platform. The camera can be installed in a forward position (fully compatible with the cleaning brush) and a rearwards position in case internal corners or very small radius transitions need to be overcome.

The camera is integrated with the 3D inspection SW and any images recorded are stored with the actual location of the captured surface as well as with distance to the camera and camera settings such as zoom, focus- and light-settings. Figure 66 shows the camera mounting positions on the BIKE.

Figure 66. Mounting of inspection camera on BIKE.

4.1.2.5 3D LIDAR

A main objective of the PILOTING project is autonomous robot activity. The BIKE was not originally equipped with anything beyond fish-eye-lens navigation cameras for environment perception. During the project, perception based on such cameras was briefly investigated and quickly dismissed due to lack of reliability and reproducibility. Based on good experience with the 2D laser

range finder used for BIKE localization, a new design was implemented to obtain a lightweight and compact reliably 3D scanning solution which can be directly mounted on and integrated with the BIKE.

A direct drive rotator with a high-resolution encoder on the driveshaft was designed to accommodate an off-the-shelf LIDAR module. For compactness reasons, the system works without a slipping and therefore can only swivel for a little more than 180 degrees. The onboard motor controller ensures smooth and precise rotation with direction changes just beyond the 180 degrees required for a full 360 degrees scan. Figure 67 shows how the basic design was realized into a working prototype.

Figure 67. Rotating 2D laser range finder design and finished hardware.

The 3D LIDAR was integrated on the BIKE with two mounting options. A forward looking one for good, unblocked view when scanning the environment as well as a rearward position for collision free compatibility with either internal corners, small radius transitions or the cleaning tool. In the rearward position, localization is still excellent and obstacle detection is still possible.

Figure 68. Mounting positions for the 3D scanning LIDAR.

4.1.2.6 Deployment Tool

A limitation for deployment of the BIKE into confined spaces are flanges which protrude into the pressure vessel with a kind of “lip” sticking out towards the inside surface. This is the result of the manufacturing process when the cylindrical flange pipe is simply cut and welded to the curved vessel

surface. Manufacturing drawings often do not specify how the flange to vessel transition truly looks like. Hence during the first PILOTING field trial, the BIKE was unable to be transferred from the flange to the vessel due to a “lip” on the inside.

To avoid any future deployment problems resulting from protruding flanges, a deployment tool was designed, which creates a curved “bridge” for the BIKE to transition over from the flange to the interior vessel surface and vice versa.

Figure 69 depicts the mechanism by which the tool is installed inside the flange. A curved, pre-bent sheet-metal bridge is inserted and pushed over the “lip”. Then the bridge is pulled back towards the access opening using a clamp-on anchoring system and a belt-tensioner. The resulting force bends the sheet metal and ensures good secure contact with the vessel interior surface as well as the lip. Once the tool is installed, the BIKE can simply drive over it. The tool can be installed in any rotation of the flange. Figure 70 shows a test-installation inside an actual pressure vessel.

Figure 69. Deployment tool for installation inside a flange or manway.

Figure 70. Deployment tool for BIKE installed inside an actual flange.

4.1.3 Final Version

Figure 71. BIKE with 3D LIDAR, inspection camera and gas sensor.

Figure 72. BIKE with PILOTING extensions.

4.1.4 Final Technical Specifications

Table 10. Final BIKE specifications.

SPEC_ID	Name and Description
RV-Spec-01	Storage temperature: -20...+70 °C
RV-Spec-02	Operating temperature: 0...+40 °C
RV-Spec-03	Weight (without cables): 9.6 kg
RV-Spec-04	Speed: - 55 ... + 55 mm/s
RV-Spec-05	Diameter range of basic BIKE platform: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • the minimum curvature required to move straight and with full steering inside a cylindrical shape (d500), • the minimum curvature required to move straight and with full steering, outside a cylindrical shape (D300), • the minimum curvature required to move straight with low steering, outside a cylindrical shape (D254),

<p>RV-Spec-06</p>	<p>Corner crossing:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Convex up to 90° • Concave up to 90°
<p>RV-Spec-07</p>	<p>Min. steering Radius 172 mm</p>
<p>RV-Spec-08</p>	<p>48V power supply via umbilical cable from external supply station</p>
<p>RV-Spec-09</p>	<p>ISC2 power consumption maximum 640W</p>
<p>RV-Spec-10</p>	<p>ICS2 input voltage 100 ... 240 VAC, 50 ... 60 Hz</p>
<p>RV-Spec-11</p>	<p>Gigabit Ethernet communication within system</p>
<p>RV-Spec-12</p>	<p>IP67 protection class</p>

<p>RV-Spec-13</p>	<p>Cleaning brush 8.3 l/s air consumption at 8 bar (max. 10 bar)</p>
<p>RV-Spec-14</p>	<p>Cleaning brush width 50 mm</p>
<p>RV-Spec-15</p>	<p>Surface curvature range with cleaning brush mounted:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Max. radius: Flat surface • Min. radius: 310mm <p>Dished vessel heads of diameters larger than 3000 mm have a corner radius above the minimum.</p>
<p>RV-Spec-16</p>	<p>Corner crossing with cleaning brush mounted</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Concave: 45° • Convex: 90°
<p>RV-Spec-17</p>	<p>Manhole minimum diameter 400 mm when cleaning brush mounted.</p>

RV-Spec-18	UT sensor dual crystal probe
RV-Spec-19	UT sensor frequency 4 MHz
RV-Spec-20	UT sensor wall thickness range 3 ... 100 mm
RV-Spec-21	UT instrument Mistras 110-LAN
RV-Spec-22	UT software EuroscanV
RV-Spec-23	HDTZ1 inspection camera Full-HD resolution
RV-Spec-24	HDTZ1 inspection camera 10x optical zoom
RV-Spec-25	HDTZ1 inspection camera flood- & spotlights with adjustable intensity
RV-Spec-26	HDTZ1 inspection camera parallel laser points for size gauging

4.2 HYBRID

4.2.1 General Overview

The HYBRID aerial robot is a specialized aircraft for inspecting magnetic pipes. This UAV is composed of two different platforms: the aerial platform, and the crawler robot, or satellite, which is responsible for performing UT inspections. The Satellite robot is gathered in the aerial platform, and it is deployed over the pipe once the HYBRID has landed on the pipe and it is attached to it, allowing for UT inspections to be carried out on the pipe.

The HYBRID System incorporates onboard sensors that provide the aircraft with the capability to autonomously navigate to the vicinity of the pipelines and, through localization techniques, precisely land on the selected pipeline and conduct UT inspections on it.

4.2.2 Modifications

After the experience in the first interaction, it became clear that a sufficiently solid landing could not be achieved and the following points for improvement were identified:

- Tilted Drone
- New landing gear for more stability on the Pipe
- New deployment system for the satellite robot
- Add sensor for relative navigation.
- Modular design

4.2.2.1 Tilted Drone

To develop this tilted aircraft, we have integrated a custom autopilot developed during the project phase, which provides us with the capability of tilted flight and designing this custom control with the aircraft's geometry. The specifications for this new autopilot are outlined below:

Table 11. Autopilot Specifications.

RV-Spec-27 Autopilot Specifications	
RV-Spec-28 Built-in Functions	
RV-Spec-29 Flight modes	RV-Spec-30 Stabilize
	RV-Spec-31 Manual Tilted
	RV-Spec-32 Altitude
	RV-Spec-33 Assisted mode (GNSS, Vision...)
	RV-Spec-34 Auto
RV-Spec-35 Fail Safe	RV-Spec-36 Stop
	RV-Spec-37 RTH
	RV-Spec-38 Landing
RV-Spec-39 Supported Airframe	RV-Spec-40 All custom drones
RV-Spec-41 Supported ESC	RV-Spec-42 400Hz refresh frequency
RV-Spec-43 Supported Receiver	RV-Spec-44 SBUS
	RV-Spec-45 ExBus
RV-Spec-46 Recommended Batteries	RV-Spec-47 3S-12S Battery (with power module)
RV-Spec-48 Communication	RV-Spec-49 Gigabit Ethernet PHY
RV-Spec-50 Barometer Accuracy	RV-Spec-51 1,5mbar
RV-Spec-52 Operation pressure	RV-Spec-53 10bar to 1,2bar
RV-Spec-54 Requirements Operation System	RV-Spec-55 Linux, QNX
RV-Spec-56 GCS	RV-Spec-57 CATEC Custom
RV-Spec-58 Additional Ports	RV-Spec-59 Serial, PWM, Can...
RV-Spec-60 Rated Power	RV-Spec-61 5W
RV-Spec-62 Weight	RV-Spec-63 86 g (without enclosure)
RV-Spec-64 Dimension	RV-Spec-65 82x110 mm
RV-Spec-66 Input Voltage	RV-Spec-67 Power Module
RV-Spec-68 Operation Temperature	RV-Spec-69 273K to 313K (0° to 40°C)

Figure 73. Top view Hybrid.

4.2.2.2 Landing gear

To achieve a more robust landing, an aircraft has been designed to distribute masses longitudinally throughout the structure, allowing for lowering the center of mass as much as possible. Additionally, a tilted configuration has been added, which provides additional degrees of freedom (DoF) that will be highly useful in this landing phase.

Figure 74. Hybrid's landed on pipe view and perspective view.

The landing system divides the landing into three phases:

- **Approach Phase:**
 - The aircraft is equipped with landing gear that guides the pipeline to the center of the airframe, aided by vision and the tilted configuration.

Figure 75. Approach phase.

- **Grasping Phase:**

- Once the drone is landed and balanced on the pipeline with active stability, the second set of landing gear engages by utilizing servomotors and friction components to securely grasp the pipeline, preventing the aircraft from falling.

Figure 76. Grasping phase.

- **Inspection Phase:**

- Once the aircraft is landed on the structure, the motors are disarmed to allow for inspections to take place.

Figure 77. Inspection phase.

4.2.2.3 Satellite Deployment System

To achieve a more robust and lightweight landing system, a deployment system based on a mechanical up-and-down mechanism, passive gripping system, and counterpoint has been designed. The landing process is divided into several phases:

- Housing phase:
- During normal operation of the aircraft, the crawler system is geometrically housed using flexible components that fit precisely into slots. A linear actuator applies a force opposite to gravity, securely locking the system in place during flight.

Figure 78. Housing phase.

- **Crawler Deployment Phase:**

- Once the aircraft has landed on the pipe, a linear actuator is activated, providing support on the pipe as a counterpoint to enhance stability and rigidity of the system.
- After securing the counterpoint, the crawler undergoes a descent using a linear actuator.

Figure 79. Crawler descent in deployment phase.

- When the crawler makes contact with the pipe, it magnetically adheres to it. The system incorporates a "T"-shaped hook made of different polymeric materials. The central section of the hook, depicted in yellow in the figure, is slightly wider and flexible. During the landing phase, the system pushes the crawler, deforming the flexible section, ensuring that the crawler is positioned on the pipe and ready for inspection.

Figure 80. Crawler adherence in deployment phase.

- **Inspection Phase:**

- Once the crawler is on the pipe, it utilizes a cable communication system. A slipping allows the cable to be coiled and uncoiled from a spool without entanglement.
- The system also includes RGB cameras to assist the operator during the inspection, release, and retrieval of the crawler.

Figure 81. Inspection Phase.

- **Crawler Retrieval Phase:**

- After inspecting the pipe, the crawler returns to the retrieval hook with the assistance of vision cameras and a V-guidance system on the hook to facilitate this process.
- With the counterpoint on the pipe, the linear actuator is activated, applying force to detach the crawler from the pipe. This force causes the hook to pass through the flexible section and remain in the retrieval position. Thanks to the counterpoint, the force is not transferred to the platform during this process.
- The crawler ascends to the four support points in the storage phase.
- The counterpoint is retrieved, and the aircraft is ready to fly again.

Figure 82. Crawler retrieval phase detail.

As an additional improvement to enhance integration, the inspection tasks were designed to make the system fully compatible with future sensors. This allows for seamless integration with the main drone using dovetail connectors, making the aircraft much more versatile.

Figure 83. Dovetail connector detail.

4.2.2.4 Sensors for Relative Navigation

To modularize the system, the sensors have been integrated using an easily interchangeable dovetail-type anchoring system on the aircraft.

Figure 84. Overall view - Relative navigation sensors.

Regarding the functionality of the sensors, we can separate them into two main groups:

- **Navigation:**

- The OSx series Ouster LiDAR has been integrated into the front area of the aircraft. This placement allows for a minimum 180-degree field of view with the entire vertical FOV available for autonomous flights. As a result, the aircraft will have the capability to autonomously navigate and avoid obstacles.

Figure 85. OSx Ouster LiDAR.

- **Pipe Detection Sensors:**

For pipe detection, a sensor fusion approach has been employed using data from multiple sensors:

- Realsense D435i: This depth sensor is mounted on a cushioned surface at a distance from the base, ensuring it does not interfere with any other sensor data and provides pipe detection information even when the aircraft is landed. By running different algorithms that estimate the relative position and orientation of the pipe below the aircraft, as well as its radius, this sensor can provide positioning data of the pipe relative to the aircraft and detect the pipe's center.

Figure 86. Depth sensor Realsense D435i.

- Hokuyo UST 10LX: This is a 2D LiDAR sensor that offers redundancy and improved pipe detection at all times. Its placement does not interfere with any other sensor, making it fully compatible with the onboard sensors.

Figure 87. Hokuyo UST 10LX LiDAR.

The overall system design has been implemented with the aim of achieving integration that allows all systems to take measurements of the pipe without interfering with each other, thus enhancing algorithm integration.

Figure 90. On board sensors.

Figure 91. On board crawler system.

Figure 92. Custom autopilot.

Figure 93. Power management.

Figure 94. Motors / PC / connections.

4.2.3 Final Version

Finally, all the proposed objectives for this aircraft have been successfully achieved. The current appearance of the system adheres to the specifications outlined in D4.1 while incorporating all the aforementioned modifications.

The attached photographic evidence highlights several notable features, including the tilted arrangement of the motors, the low center of mass, the equipment distribution, and the modular electronics.

Figure 95. HYBRID system.

4.2.4 Final Technical Specifications

Table 12. Final HYBRID specifications.

SPEC_ID	Name and Description
HY-Spec-01	Size of the robot (in mm)

HY-Spec-02	Operating temperature: 0...+40 °C
HY-Spec-03	Maximum takeoff weight: 28 Kg
HY-Spec-04	Weight with standard equipment and batteries: 15 Kg
HY-Spec-05	Free-flight positioning precision using GNSS: Vertical 0,5 m, horizontal 1,5 m.
HY-Spec-06	Positioning precision using Lidar: Vertical 0,05 m, horizontal 0,05 m
HY-Spec-07	Maximum wind resistance while flying: 10 m/s
HY-Spec-08	Maximum wind resistance while landing on pipe: 4 m/s
HY-Spec-09	Standard configuration flight time: 7 min
HY-Spec-10	Minimum pipe diameter: 8 inches
HY-Spec-11	Batteries specifications: 4 units of 6S (25 V) and 12 Ah capacity.
HY-Spec-12	Wireless communications over proprietary ubiquity Wi-Fi protocol.
HY-Spec-13	Cable communications over ethernet gigabit cable
HY-Spec-14	Satellite speed 100 mm/s
HY-Spec-15	Satellite weight 0.8 kg
HY-Spec-16	Satellite power supply 24 ... 26 V
HY-Spec-17	Satellite maximum power consumption 28.5 W
HY-Spec-18	Satellite Size 138 x 171 x 90 mm
HY-Spec-19	Satellite minimum height clearance 100 mm
HY-Spec-20	Satellite control ethernet interface

HY-Spec-21	Satellite navigation camera resolution HD 1080p
HY-Spec-22	Satellite video 5.8 GHz A/V interface
HY-Spec-23	Satellite umbilical length 2 m
HY-Spec-24	Satellite protection rating IP 3x
HY-Spec-25	Satellite diameter range for navigation OD 200 ... ID 300 mm
HY-Spec-26	Satellite diameter range for inspection OD 200 ... flat
HY-Spec-27	Satellite maximum Surface temperature 0 ... 80 °C
HY-Spec-28	Satellite maximum coating thickness 0.3 mm
HY-Spec-29	Satellite UTM thickness range 3 ... 100 mm
HY-Spec-30	Satellite UTM sensor dual crystal with 8 mm element size
HY-Spec-31	Satellite UTM sensor frequency 4 MHz
HY-Spec-32	Satellite UTM Lemo 00 connector

5. Conclusions

Describing the final stage of the development of all PILOTIONG robotic platforms, this document clearly shows the efforts which went into adapting the platforms to suit the requirements of their respective use-cases. Based on findings from experiments and field trials, some platforms underwent fundamental re-designs while others were selectively improved and equipped with hardware to achieve the overall performance.

When comparing the state of the platforms with their first iterations presented in deliverable D4.1, it is clearly noticeable that the project methodology was very successful. The strategy of performing field experiments using preliminary versions of the platforms and leaving sufficient time and resources afterwards for a second iteration led to significant improvements, well aligned with user- and project-requirements.